

THE IMPACT OF DIGITALIZATION OF ACCOUNTING SYSTEM ON ACCOUNTANTS**Dr Jeet Singh**Head, Department of Commerce, Government Degree College, MJP Rohilkhand University, Bareilly,
India, Email: jsy2626@rediffmail.com**Abstract:**

The time of relying on the traditional methods of accounting is gone now. The accountants of the today's digital era should be ready with the technological skill-set to overcome the problems of the dynamic business world. The accountants should go ahead but with ethics. Digitalization enables the business organizations to grow at a rapid pace by changing their business and operating model. Therefore, firms need to be prepared for new adjustments. It is a need of an hour that Chartered Accountants, Cost and Management Accountants and other accountants must adopt the rapid and quick advances in accounting technology if they do not want to become irrelevant in the accounting industry. This needs staying up-to-date with technological advancement and trends, current accounting software to meet the needs of business organizations, and being open to embrace and learn new and advancing technologies. As technology will keep on changing at a rapid speed, accountants who have not only fundamental IT skills but also adaptability along with flexibility in their approach will always be prepared to amalgamate new and more efficient tools into existing accounting processes. In today's dynamic business and economic environment accounting industry changing now. The change is at rapid pace and largely driven by innovative advances in technology. In several ways, the pandemic has accelerated that change and adoption of technology. The business world is moving ahead and developing a lot with the emergence of digital revolutions and there is no exception to accounting functions. Companies started to accept the new technology and understood the importance of the digitalization and its implication in data security, storage as well as its importance in improving the accounting services. The use and application of digitalization by many business organizations affected the price of these digital technologies and reduced the prices for internet-based technologies, software, and programs. The present paper looks into the impact of digitalization of accounting system on accountants. The present paper analyzes the cost and benefit of digital accounting. The paper highlights the digital tools used in digital accounting and assesses the steps involved in digital accounting. The paper concludes with the fact that rather than worry about artificial intelligence and data driven technology taking over their jobs, accountants should hug this technology as a powerful key to improve customer services. The new technology will not replace the accountants but support them because **human experience, human interaction, human trust, human compassion is inevitable to improve customer services and these important things will not be available from technology**. Accountants do not have to worry about being replaced by artificial intelligence and data driven technology and automation. Though their duties may change and they have to hug this technology, but that is part of every task or job. Digitalization will actually make the accountant's job easier in many ways.

Keywords: Digital Accounting, accountants, cloud accounting, artificial intelligence, big data

1. Introduction

Technology has transformed how we live and work. Demographic shifts have reshaped the society and the workforce. Liberalization, Privatization and Globalization has changed the rules across the world markets. Customer expectations have dramatically increased, expecting everything faster, better, more differentiated and personalized than before. Now it is not a question before the organizations whether

to digitalize or not. Rather organizations are focusing on how fast they equipped with digitalization and remain relevant to their customers. The traditional tools with which we are associated are now being replaced by new and innovative technologies.

In order to compete effectively in today's markets, companies need to be competitive simultaneously on quality, price, delivery, responsiveness, innovation and consistently creating value. Here Finance and Accounts Manager has to play a crucial role. When accountancy is designed to meet the needs of the present or current digital economy we call it digital accounting. Large scale companies can afford to adopt digital accounting. Looking at micro, small and medium organizations, they play a major role in the development of Indian economy. So, a regular restructuring of MSMEs is a need of an hour where digital transformation can play a defining role. It is essential for these MSMEs to adopt digital accounting which will bring them various benefits for the in performing accounting operations. It will make their accounting functions more effective and efficient by planning, organizing and satisfactorily channelizing their financial processes and system. Digital accounting will help in automation of time consuming and repetitive tasks as well as redefine existing business processes.

Digital accounting is concerned with the creation, representation, and transfer of financial information in an electronic format. All accounting transactions are conducted in an electronic environment rather using paper.

2. Review of Literature

According to Daugherty & Wilson (2018) it is a misconception to think that machines will gradually replace humans in labour markets. They think the man-versus-machine view is old-fashioned and short-sighted. Instead we should start to think about it as collaboration between humans and machines.

According to Charles Hoffman (2017) there are three technological innovations that are primarily driving the changes of the current accounting practices, methods and procedures and which can noticeably modernize and improve accounting and auditing.

In another research recently done by Zhang, Dai and Vasarhelyi (2018) the focus is on the impacts of disruptive technologies and how it will change the accounting and auditing profession as well as the education. As for to today there is still a lack of Information technology in the education which means that the students aren't prepared for the accounting workplace of the future. The most important question is about how the profession is going to adapt to the technological changes and how it will change the traditional procedures.

The standardization of accounting reports is one of the reasons that prompted accounting functions to automate their accounting processes which are known as automated accounting. Automated accounting has been growing vastly and is still growing (Uwadiae, 2015).

Previous researches show that there is either relation or no relation between the firm characteristics and the use of digitalization in the firm (Level of digitalization in the firm). Gibbs & Kraemer (2004) discuss that bigger firms are more likely to have more knowledge about the impact of technology compared to the smaller sized companies. Bresnahan et al (2002) discuss that firms that hire more employees with university degrees use digital technologies more than other firms do.

Technological changes can interrupt the accounting function and at the same time evolve within the accounting profession. These changes may have a significant impact on accounting functions and it also proves the new argument that profession will become different in the future (Gould, 2017).

3. Research Methodology

The present study has been undertaken to analyze the **impact of digitalization of accounting system on accountants**. The paper is not confined to any particular area; on the other hand it is applicable to whole India. However, opinion of entrepreneurs/managers of various companies in Moradabad district of Uttar Pradesh has been taken about the feasibility of digital accounting. Their views have been incorporated in this paper. The paper also takes the references of various articles written by various experts on digital accounting and its impact on accountants.

4. Objectives Of The Study

The present study aims at the following objectives:

1. To analyze the impact of digitalization of accounting system on accountants;
2. To analyze the cost and benefit of digital accounting;
3. To highlight the digital tools used in digital accounting;
4. To assess the steps involved in digital accounting.

• Steps Involved in Introducing Digital Accounting in an Organization

Look into the current scenario in an organization: The first step involves the analysis of the objective of the firm, its processes and the work flow system. Assess the clients and resources to adopt the digitalization process.

1. **Defining the goals:** Before adopting digital accounting, look into the goals the firm wants to achieve. Creation of roadmap to the end objective is essential. Assessment of firm's areas of improvement is essential.
2. **Review of Services offered:** The firm must reassess the services offered by it. Digitalization will enable the firm to expand the service line which it is currently offering.
3. **Selection of appropriate technology:** Technology is an essential ingredient of digitalization. The firm has to choose the right software which can provide a competitive advantage. The technology to be chosen should be depend on the size of the firm, requirement of clients, expertise area of the firm, requirement of present and future needs.
4. **Recruitment of workforce:** The right workforce should be hired which should be digitally savvy. The existing staff should be trained to transform them to be fit in the digitally environment. Though, it will increase the cost but it will give more revenue to the firm.
5. **Digital accounting tools and techniques:** Various tools and techniques will be required for digital accounting such as electronic ledger keepers, integrated document management systems, e-invoicing, automatic recording and online storage of invoices.

5. Digital Tools in Digital Accounting

During decades, the accounting has shifted from paper based to computer based. Now there is a large technological shift i.e. digitalization. This large shift involves, cloud accounting, Internet of Things, Block chain, Big data and tools for visualization, etc. Now many day to day accounting works have been replaced with modern technology. Many tasks are bulk imitation of vouchers, creation of vouchers, voucher auditing, complete GST summary, finding average as well as minimum and maximum cash balance in a month or year, sorting of vouchers amount-wise, and many more. These tasks are now very easy to handle due to the introduction of various digital solutions like real-time reporting, data quality management, paperless or digital accounting, big-data analysis, and cloud computing, etc.

So, the various digital tools involved in digital accounting are mentioned herein below:

- 1) **Cloud Accounting:** As per cloud suppliers cloud implementation is fast as there is no need to download or install any software. All users can have access to the same version of application at one time. As long as internet connection is available, all data and information are available anytime and from anywhere on any device. Also, cloud accounting released the unnecessary data, so accountants does not burdened with irrelevant data. The cloud helps the users to edit the same files on the cloud. This enables the other users to have access to the updated financial data or information as cloud automatically changes the information. Cloud makes a backup of the information automatically which keeps the information safer. Previously company needs to buy or upgrade the hardware to store heavy files but now the company can choose to improve and expand the storage space and it is less costly than the traditional one.
- 2) **Internet of Things:** In accounting, the usage of Internet of Things (IoT) begins with the requirement for connection between all parts of the business process in order to create efficiency in the process of financial accounting. With the help of IoT, data is transferred and delivered to other devices more securely and safely.
- 3) **Artificial Intelligence (AI):** AI is very helpful for professionals of accounting and finance to be more productive. Artificial intelligence allows machines to take repetitive, redundant and time consuming financial work. Use of machines enables to reduce costs and errors by streamlining operations. New innovative technology has changed the clients' expectations while working with companies which are also true for accounting. Artificial accounting helps the accountants to be more productive and efficient.
- 4) **Blockchain:** Blockchain was developed when bitcoin proposed for the first time in the year 2008. The blockchain is considered as a digitized ledger which records the transactions without any involvement of any financial intermediate. In blockchain, storage spaces are there in which data are recorded and it is called block. Each and every block works in the nature of real time general ledger. Each block is concerned with storage of permanent information related to previous transaction and as soon as block is completed it will attach to the next block and gives it away. All these blocks are connected to each other and have particular information about the previous block for safety matter. All these blocks are joined and connected to each other in a linked chain and therefore, this technique is called blockchain.
- 5) **Big Data:** Among the financial and business industries, big data have been used significantly in the past. To make financial and business decisions, data is crucial. In today's dynamic environment data is not just numbers and spreadsheets that accountants have been working with for many years, on the other hand, it also includes unstructured data that can be investigated, scrutinized and analyzed through natural language processing. Even audit process has been digitized. Big data consists of enormous collection of data which is of huge size, so it is not possible to analyse it manually or using traditional accounting software. With big data accounting entries would be automated. Here it is important to state that the role of an accountant is significant and the position of an accountant will not vanish. Rather the demand for accountants will rise who are able to work and have good knowledge of interpretation and handle the analysis of financial data.
- 6) **Tools for Visualization:** In financial reporting, visualization of data is increasingly common. Many companies are using data visualization tools to analyse the big amount of data stores in their financial and information system. For instance, graphs, tables and other indicators are used which are suitable and common to use. Decision makers as well as accountants can compare

different types of visualization tools and choose the best one for their task. So, the visualization tools have a major role in representing data more simple and easy to understand.

- 7) **Autonomous Robots:** It is not essential that Robots should be physical entities. As far as accounting and finance is concerned, robotic process automation can handle time consuming as well as repetitive tasks, for instance, document analysis and processing, which is plentiful in any accounts department. With the help of autonomous robots, accountants find time to work on strategy and advisory work

6. Impact of Digitalization of Accounting System on Accountants

It is a fact that artificial intelligence can handle many standard accounting tasks more efficiently and faster but it does not mean that role of accountants will diminish. Always, there will be a need for human touch, human element and human intelligence. In various reports it is said that artificial intelligence will create more jobs than it will replace.

The impact of digitalization of accounting system on accountants can be analyzed in the following points:

1. Accountants must now worry much more about adaptation of new technology than replacement. Data driven technologies along with digitalization and automation are poised to free accountants rather constrain them. Business organizations that move ahead towards digitalization and understand the importance of data driven technologies and invest to a great extent in providing tools, techniques and training of accountants will take a lead and advantage in the long run.
2. There is no worry on the part of accountants for being replaced by artificial intelligence in near future. Business organizations will always require accountants that will be helpful in analyzing and interpreting artificial intelligence data. So, instead of replacing the accountant, artificial intelligence technology will transform the duties which accountant performs. Artificial intelligence will help the accountants to improve their services.
3. Today's accountant is not burdened with task oriented projects rather they are business advisors and experts in various teams of an organization. The job of an accountant is much easier due to the introduction of data driven technology. The ability of an accountant to analyze statistical data has been increased due to increase in the knowledge of technology. Now accountants can interpret statistical data more efficiently and effectively and this is due to the technological advancement.
4. Accountants can use their human skills to transform the new insights taken from high quality data into effective financial planning and reporting.
5. Upcoming accountants will definitely play a more strategic and creative role in their organizations as a result of which business organizations will enjoy more efficient workflows and enhance their competitive footing in the business environment.
6. They can collaborate with colleagues/peers from other departments and business units to leverage financial data to drive innovation and develop business plans so as to promote growth along with ensuring continuity. They can do their best in building more flexible and responsive supply chains.
7. With digitalization it is hoped that the skill set as well as job description for accountants will be greatly expanded. The accounting teams in an organization with the support of technology will be populated with dedicated accounting professionals as well as subject experts from different areas of business.

8. The new accountant's role will change from a traditional accountant to an advisory role and work for charting a strategic sourcing plan.
9. With the support of new technology and digitalization of accounting work, accountants can acquire greater technical acumen and diverse skills which enables them to bring their expertise to different organizational teams as a result of which they can provide crucial financial intelligence, refine budgets and ensuring compliances of various rules and regulations.
10. More focus should be on core competencies, lifelong learning and education and skill development which are needed to handle the dynamic environment of business.
11. Increased regulations and globalization will impact the demand for accountants in the future. Though many accounting tasks are digitalized, accountants will never be replaced by technology because technology cannot solve the client's problems, also technology will never be able to handle client's queries as it is done by accountants. It can be said that that in future accountants will have the opportunity to develop more advanced skills so that they can act as business advisors/consultants along with strategic partners rather simple financial experts.
12. Future accountants have to develop technological skills because business organizations seek technology expertise and the reason is that finance department of any organization moves from reporting function to analytics centric function.
13. Now accountants must acquire the following skills in order to survive in digital environment:
 - Advanced Excel Skills – to solve complex problems.
 - Knowledge of business intelligence softwares – to enhance transparency and reduce costs.
 - Understanding Enterprise Resource Planning System – to gain competitive edge and reduce cycle times.
 - Expertise in data analytics – to add value due to handle large amount of data.
 - Understanding cloud computing – to increase efficiency and flexibility.
14. In order to survive in digitalized environment, accountants need to acquire the following skills to work efficiently and effectively:
 - Analytical Skills – to turn Big Data into concise and decision driving insights.
 - Communication Skills – to convey important financial information to top management and stakeholders
 - Relationship Skills – to manage numbers and people, to motivate and engage employees.
 - Creativity – to solve financial and non-financial problems faster and in effective manner.
 - Business Acumen – to understand the business as a whole. The ability to see the big picture as how each functional area works to its best.
 - Tech Savvy- to be ready to use new technology every time.

In order to acquire IT skills accountants need to attend seminars and conferences, learn through online programmes or attend college level courses. Due to dynamic business environment, accountants must remain updated on the latest development in the areas of accounting, technologies and industry.

7. Cost and Benefit Analysis of Digital Accounting

When a company adopt a new system it looks for cost associated with it as well as benefits derived from the new system. Proper analysis is essential as to how much digital accounting will cost to the company and what benefits will accrue from it. The cost and benefit analysis is highlighted below:

Cost associated with digital accounting:

- Initial requirement for expensive experts and consultants;

- Heavy investment required in laptops, computer hardware as well as software;
- Expenses involved in processes, systems, processing of information and changes in report generation;
- Training of accounting personnel;
- Cost involved in security, control and audit requirements for financial transactions during the initial stage;
- Initial configuration of the system or integration with enterprise resource planning software is not correct, results in recurring costs;
- Resistance from users;

Benefits accrued from digital accounting:

- Geographical reach is extended ore becomes broad;
- Posting of transactions, payments, collections, reports generation, credit approvals, etc becomes faster, so there is a faster cycle times;
- Access of data 24/7, there is a continuous availability of services;
- Internal and external customers are highly satisfied;
- Requirement of accounting staff becomes less;
- Productivity is improved;
- Saves employees' time and improves productivity by allowing them to engage the saved time on other productive work or task.
- Error rates are reduced;
- Better cash management i.e. efficient payments and collection system;
- Paper work is reduced;
- Reduction in routine clerical activity through automated documentation
- Expenses on paper are reduced;
- Automated budgetary control and variance analysis;
- Improved audit trials
- Improvement in data security;

8. Conclusion

Once upon a time accountants spent their full time in doing manual entries and searching for errors and mistakes. But with the development of computer based technology this scenario is completely changed. In today's digital era, accountants can complete their task in a very less time and their focus is now shifted towards analysis of statistical data and advise and consultation. To conclude it can be said that automation brings greater opportunities for the accountants because it enables minimizing transactional and other routine tasks viz. data entry, bookkeeping and other compliance work. Automation provides accountants to focus efficiently and effectively on value added services.

In today's dynamic environment, technology is transforming in addition to core operational areas of organizations (like value-added supply chain) the central functions including HR, Finance and Purchasing, etc. The technological disruption is also being observed in accounting processes and system at a very high speed. The new and innovative digital tools are helping the accountants especially Chartered Accountants, Cost Accountants, etc in carrying out their duties accurately, effortlessly and in a speedy way. The digital accounting enables the organizations to serve their customers with convenience and in easy way and efficiently manage their operations. When we look at post-pandemic world, business organizations will have to hug the digitization in order to survive and overcome challenges. It is true that there are many accounting tasks and functions that can be automated; but there

is a lack of knowledge and understanding of these technologies and a lack of financial resources to adopt and implement them.

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